

Evaluating The Diagnostic Efficacy Of Diffusion Weighted Imaging And Susceptibility Weighted Imaging Sequences In MRI For Detecting Acute Stroke

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Received: May 05, 2025

Accepted: Jun 06, 2025

Published: Jun 07, 2025

Abstract

Background: Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) plays a vital role not only in the detection of ischemic lesions but also in various other diagnostic applications. Susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI) represents a novel approach within the realm of magnetic resonance techniques, focusing on the identification of magnetic susceptibility differences among different tissue types, including iron, blood, and calcifications. The primary objective of this study was to emphasize the significance of incorporating susceptibility-weighted MR images alongside diffusion-weighted images for the purpose of diagnosing acute stroke cases within the brain.

OBJECTIVES:

- Evaluate the effectiveness of Diffusion-Weighted Imaging (DWI) and Susceptibility-Weighted Imaging (SWI) in MRI for diagnosing acute stroke.
- Identify any correlations between DWI and SWI findings and the severity or location of acute stroke lesions.
- To compare the diagnostic performance of DWI and SWI for acute ischemic stroke detection and assess the correlation between SWI findings and clinical outcomes in stroke patients

METHODS: a prospective cross-sectional study was conducted reviewing 87 patients request and reports that had MRI. Brain scan with a history of stroke. A period of 6 months from January 25 to May 2025. The information obtained was recorded on a self-designed data capture sheet. Data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2011.

RESULT: This study evaluated 87 patients with acute stroke, revealing a variety of pathologies and abnormalities. Ischemic stroke was the most prevalent, accounting for 71% of cases, followed by haemorrhagic stroke (29%). The majority of patients were male (72%), aged 18-95 (28%), and had infracts on the right side (31%), left side (52%), and left side (17%). The type of infract in the brain

was also varied, with hyperintense signals in 63 patients and no signals in 24 patients. DWI MRI brain examinations were the most common, with 77 patients having hyperintense signals and 10 having hypointense signals.

CONCLUSION: Although CT is not found out the stroke <6 hr. in this time period, MRI is the only imaging modality to rule out the stroke lesion. DWI is the old techniques to identify acute or chronic infarct. SWI has great impact on the diagnosis of haemorrhagic stroke that only can SWI can do. It can differentiate between haemorrhage & calcification. Advanced post processing techniques magnitude phase & mip images are very helpful diagnosis purpose

Keyword : MRI, Strokes, Infarct, Acute , DWI, SWI, Hemorrhage.

Introductions : Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has transformed the area of medical imaging since its beginnings, delivering unique insights into the human body without the use of ionizing radiation. As a non-invasive imaging modality, MRI combines powerful magnetic fields and radiofrequency pulses to generate high-resolution images of soft tissues, making it a crucial tool in the diagnosis and management of a wide range of medical disorders.⁽¹⁾ MRI has become essential in many clinical specialties, such as neurology, oncology, cardiology, and musculoskeletal medicine, due to its capacity to generate precise anatomical and functional images.⁽²⁾ When it comes to detecting acute stroke, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is essential, especially when using diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) and susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI). While SWI improves the visualization of venous architecture and microbleeds, DWI is very good at detecting regions of restricted water diffusion. These two techniques provide complimentary information for a precise stroke assessment³. A more sophisticated understanding of stroke pathophysiology is made possible by the incorporation of DWI and SWI into MRI techniques. For prompt therapeutic approaches, DWI is very sensitive to early ischemic alterations, frequently identifying cytotoxic oedema minutes after symptoms appear. SWI, on the other hand, takes use of the variations in magnetic susceptibility across different tissues, which enables it to detect hemorrhagic changes and venous congestion that may be present in conjunction with ischemic strokes⁽²⁾

When there is sudden bleeding in the brain or when blood flow to the brain is interrupted, a stroke may result. Two categories of strokes exist. An ischemic stroke is a stroke caused by a blockage in blood flow to the brain. The blood cannot supply the brain with nutrition and oxygen. Within minutes, brain cells start to die in the absence of oxygen and nutrition. A hemorrhagic stroke is one that happens as a result of sudden bleeding in the brain. The blood leak hurts brain cells by pressing on them, which can cause damage.

Less than 90% of strokes are ischemic (caused by blocked blood arteries), with hemorrhagic strokes accounting for the remaining strokes. The location of the obstruction or bleeding in the brain determines the subsequent classification of strokes. MRI is an application of the principle of nuclear magnetic resonance imaging (NMR) in which the distribution of hydrogen atoms in the patient's tissues is examined. It uses a combination of strong magnetic field and radio waves to produce detailed images of almost every internal structure in the human body, including the organs, bones, muscles and blood vessels. The process involves placing the patient inside a large cylindrical machine that contains powerful magnets.⁽⁴⁾

In 1997, Haacke introduced and patented SWI imaging, which became available on commercial scanners after 2004. This technique helps detect certain substances in the brain, like ferritin and hemosiderin, that can appear after bleeding. These substances affect the MRI signal, making it easier to identify areas of bleeding. SWI imaging highlights differences in tissues that show signs of recent bleeding, blood clots, or other changes, which is particularly useful for evaluating strokes. It makes haemorrhages much more visible—about six times more so than traditional methods. Therefore, it should be a standard part of brain imaging for stroke assessments.⁽⁵⁾

DWI Sequence Is Most Commonly Performed MRI sequences for the detection of the acute stroke & is very sensitive to very small and early infarcts. conventionally use MRI sequences like (T1W, T2W, FLAIR) They cannot identify the early acute stroke within 12 hr. & small infarcts also cannot be visualized by the modern multi detector computed tomography scanner.⁽⁶⁾

A relatively large number of intracranial diseases may exhibit restricted diffusion, thus appearing bright on diffusion-weighted imaging. Restricted diffusion usually manifests within 30-120 minutes following a cerebral infarction and typically returns to normal within 10-14 days. The DW pulse sequence is initially conducted with the diffusion gradients (DG's) either turned off or set to a minimal value. This process produces a series of b₀ images, which are T2-weighted and act as a baseline for subsequent map calculations. In abdominal imaging, b₅₀ images are frequently acquired, as the slight yet non-zero gradient amplitude aids in vessel signal suppression.^(5,6)

The DW sequence is executed with the diffusion gradients (DG's) activated either individually or in combination at varying intensities. This process yields DW source images that are sensitized to diffusion across various directions.⁽⁷⁾

DW source images are merged to create a series of Trace DW images, which are the primary images utilized for clinical diagnosis. Subsequently, an Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC) map is generated from the data of the b₀ and source images. This ADC map aids in the delineation of abnormalities observed in the trace images. Additional advanced processing may be conducted as an option, yielding further calculated image sets for detailed analysis. Such sets can encompass exponential ADC maps, images of fractional anisotropy, maps indicating the principal direction of diffusion, and Fiber tracking maps.⁸

Susceptibility is a measure of the extent to which a substance becomes magnetized when it is placed in an external magnetic field. A synonym for susceptibility is "magnetizability".

Most biological tissues exhibit weak diamagnetic properties. However, some tissues are paramagnetic due to concentrated amounts of metals such as iron, gadolinium, copper, or manganese, which intensify the magnetic field. Moreover, some tissues contain superparamagnetic aggregates of proteins, like ferritin and hemosiderin, that are rich in iron.

Susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI) enables the detection and characterization of tissue components based on their varying susceptibilities.⁹

Diffusion working principle- Modern diffusion-weighted (DW) imaging techniques can trace their roots back to the pulsed gradient spin echo (PGSE) method, which was pioneered by Edward Stejskal and John Tanner in the mid-1960s. In this approach, strong and symmetric diffusion-

sensitizing gradients (DGs) are applied on either side of a 180° pulse. This setup ensures that the phases of stationary spins remain unchanged, as any phase shift caused by the first gradient lobe is countered by the second. In contrast, spins that are diffusing move to different locations between the two gradient lobes, resulting in a loss of coherence and a decrease in signal intensity.

Following the application of the second DG, an image acquisition sequence is initiated, typically utilizing an echo-planar imaging technique. This method employs rapidly oscillating phase and frequency gradients to produce multiple gradient echoes. Quick image acquisition is crucial to reduce the impact of bulk motion, such as vascular pulsations, on the resulting diffusion-weighted images. While other imaging modules, like fast spin echo, can be used, they are not as commonly employed in contemporary practice.¹⁰

Modern diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) techniques build upon the foundational principles of the original pulsed gradient spin echo (PGSE) method developed by Stejskal and Tanner, incorporating several enhancements. To mitigate chemical shift artifacts, all commercially available DWI sequences implement some form of fat suppression. This can be achieved through a chemically-selective fat saturation pulse or a nonselective "STIR-like" inversion pulse applied just before the 90° pulse. Alternatively, the 90° pulse may be specifically tuned to excite only water protons.

To address issues related to eddy currents and minimize spatial distortion artifacts, a "twice-refocused" PGSE sequence is often employed. This approach includes an additional 180° refocusing pulse right before the image acquisition phase begins. Another common strategy to further reduce eddy current artifacts is the use of bipolar diffusion gradients instead of unipolar ones. These modifications collectively enhance the quality and reliability of DWI, making it a more effective tool for clinical and research applications.¹¹

The steps required for to generate DWI Image -

1. At First DW Pulse Sequence Turned on With the Diffusion Gradient Turned Off or Set to A Very Low Value Depends Upon the Body Part Is Examined like b_0 , images are provided they are most properly T2W images.
2. In next step the diffusion gradients are turned on different strength & time this produce the source DW image, they are sensitive to detect diffusion in different direction.
3. The DW source image and different strength image are combined to make trace DW image, they are using d_{in} in the clinical purpose.
4. ADC (apparent diffusion coefficient) map is produced by the b_0 image and source image, adc map is clarify any abnormality or any restricted diffusion seen on trace image.
5. Additional advanced processing techniques can be applied to generate supplementary calculated image sets for in-depth analysis. These may encompass exponential apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) maps, fractional anisotropy images, principal diffusion direction maps, and Fiber tracking maps. Such enhancements provide valuable insights into the underlying microstructural properties of tissues, facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of the data.¹¹

Uses-

Acute brain ischemia-Early stroke detection, differentiating acute vs chronic stroke. The b-values up-to 1000 are used for standard neuroimaging application.

Brain tumors- Tumors with high cellularity, such as high-grade glioma, medulloblastoma, and central nervous system lymphoma, have been shown to have lower ADC levels. Higher tumor grades and a worse prognosis have been linked to lower ADC readings. ADC quantitative evaluations have been useful in predicting treatment outcomes. This measure works very well for detecting pseudo-progression and pseudo-response. A situation known as pseudo-response happens after anti-angiogenic therapy, in which the tumor does not show improvement even if it is still viable or is really progressing. Even in the absence of contrast enhancement, diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) can be used to show the existence of ongoing or growing tumor activity. When edema results from an inflammatory reaction instead of the actual advancement of the tumor, pseudo-progression is seen alongside it.⁽¹³⁾

- **White matter diseases**- microstructural changes can be detected by DW MR. White matter changes in tissue orientation that's make anisotropy diffusion, that can be detected by DTI (diffusion tensor imaging). Examples include multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer disease, leukoencephalopathies, Wallerian degeneration, Cerebral Autosomal Dominant Arteriopathy with Subcortical Infarcts and Leukoencephalopathy and HIV-1 encephalopathy.

Oncological applications-In the area of onco-imaging, diffusion-weighted imaging has great potential. Malignant lesions have lower ADC values compared to surrounding normal tissue. benign tumors in brain, head and neck malignancies, prostate and liver cancer can be quantified in terms of ADC values. Recent applications of DWI in oncology include evaluation of response to chemoradiotherapy. Increase in ADC value can be detected before the size of the tumor decreases.

- **Breast cancer**-observed that malignant breast tumors have considerably lower ADC values than benign illnesses ($1.36 \pm 0.36 \times 10^{-3}$ vs $2.01 \pm 0.46 \times 10^{-3}$) with b values up to 400 s/mm². It is currently a standard component of the multi-parametric MR assessment of breast masses. Not only on the above-mentioned field have use of DWI imaging. Dwi Imaging Has A Great Impact on Modern Radiological Procedure.¹³

SWI Sequence working principle - Susceptibility serves as an indicator of the degree to which a material acquires magnetization upon exposure to an external magnetic field. A term that can be utilized interchangeably with susceptibility is "magnetizability." When matter engages with the magnetic field, an internal magnetization or polarization (J) is generated, which may either counteract or enhance the external field. J represents a quantum phenomenon that is predominantly influenced by the interactions of electrons with the external magnetic field. Depends on the polarization the magnetic susceptibility varies with external magnetic field if the polarization opposite to applied field the effect is known as diamagnetism. If polarization in same direction the effect is known as a Para magnetism, ferromagnetism. From this ratio of the two magnetic field diamagnetic substance have negative susceptibilities & paramagnetic, ferromagnetic substance have positive susceptibilities, we all know that nearly all biological tissues are weakly diamagnetic. However, some tissues are paramagnetic because You have focused on areas with high concentrations of metals like iron, gadolinium, copper, or manganese, which tend to attract magnetic fields. Tissues that contain iron-based proteins, such as ferritin and hemosiderin, are

referred to as superparamagnetic. Susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI) is a technique that helps detect and analysed different tissue components by looking at how they respond to magnetic susceptibility differences.⁸

Susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI) has progressed from rudimentary two-dimensional T2*-weighted sequences to advanced three-dimensional sequences characterized by enhanced spatial resolution and superior susceptibility contrast. SWI represents a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) sequence that exhibits heightened sensitivity to substances which induce perturbations in the local magnetic field, such as calcium and iron, wherein the phase information allows for distinctive differentiation. Nevertheless, the designation "SWI" is commonly employed to refer to high-spatial-resolution susceptibility-enhanced sequences across various MRI manufacturers and modalities, even in instances where phase information is not incorporated. The imaging characteristics of SWI and its related sequences are significantly influenced by the specific acquisition methodologies employed¹⁴ At the outset, SWI and analogous sequences were predominantly utilized to augment the visualization of abnormalities already identifiable through conventional two-dimensional T2*-weighted neuroimaging: an increased incidence of microbleeds in elderly patients or those with dementia or mild traumatic brain injury; enhanced visibility of superficial siderosis in Alzheimer's disease and amyloid angiopathy; as well as iron accumulation in neurodegenerative disorders or atypical vascular formations such as capillary telangiectasia. Furthermore, the peripheral rim sign in abscesses, arterial signal attenuation associated with thrombus, symmetrically prominent cortical veins in stroke, and intra-tumoral susceptibility signals in cerebral neoplasm. The influence of localised field variations caused by tissue constituents, such as blood products (e.g., hemosiderin in cerebral microbleeds), iron content (often exhibited as ferritin), calcium content, and deoxyhaemoglobin present in venous blood, is purposefully amplified in T2*-weighted, susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI), or SWI-like procedures¹⁵. Localised magnetic field fluctuations caused by these processes lead to signal attenuation that is typified by T2* effects. Traditionally, a two-dimensional gradient-echo T2*-weighted sequence was used for evaluating susceptibility effects. these sequences included a small flip angle, which made the pictures mostly spin-density weighted and improved the contrast between the cerebrospinal fluid and surrounding tissues. Since the appearance of cerebral microbleeds depends on both TE and spatial resolution, only bigger microbleeds could be seen at TEs of 20 to 25 milliseconds at 1.5 Tesla. Significantly smaller microbleeds can be seen using high-spatial-resolution three-dimensional gradient-echo sequences, especially when prolonged TEs are used. Spin dephasing, which depends on the precession imaging sequence, causes susceptibility-related signal attenuation when it occurs in the presence of localised magnetic field changes. The main differences between these approaches are whether T2* is used alone or in conjunction with phase measurements. Because T2* effects are more prominent with longer echo times, using only T2* produces less contrast than SWI, although it is still effective at higher field strengths¹⁶

Physical parameter –

- Typical imaging parameters include $TR = 25-50$ ms, $TE = 20-40$ ms, and flip angles = $15-20^\circ$. Shorter times and smaller flip angles are used as field strength increases.
- SWI sequences are generated from the gradient echo (GRE) pulse sequence.

- These sequences are very sensitive to difference in tissue susceptibility because they have not the ability to refocus the spin dephased by magnetic field inhomogeneities.
- Traditional T2* weighted GRE sequence can differentiate between blood, calcium and iron product.
- Modern swi sequences acquired image in 3d, allowing thin section & small voxel size is achieved. Flow compensation is used to reduced artifact.
- Acceleration factors are used to reduce image acquisition time, or single shot image acquisition can be achieved in a given TR interval.
- The ability to analyse and display magnitude and phase data individually, as well as combine them for diagnostic purposes, is a fundamental component of SWI.
- The magnitude image, which shows background tissue with spin-density-like contrast, is stored for diagnostic use.
- Raw Phase data are prepared for the clinical purpose by further post processing; raw phase images are passing by digital high pass filter to reduce the inhomogeneities as well as distortions due to the air and bone at the skull.
- Phase correction algorithms are used to reduce the artifact.
- At the end of the result, we get the filtered phase image images that are saved for the diagnostic purpose. The number of original 3D source images that are stacked together determines the thickness of the minimum intensity projections (MIPs) of the SW image that are normally shown.
- Every MR vendor have own name of swi sequence, GE offers SWAN (Susceptibility Weighted Angiography), Philips offers SWIp (*SWI-phase*, formerly called Veno BOLD), Hitachi has BSI (Blood Sensitive Imaging), and Canon offers FSBB (Flow Sensitive Black Blood)¹⁷.

OBJECTIVE:

- To compare Evaluate the effectiveness of Diffusion-Weighted Imaging (DWI) and Susceptibility-Weighted Imaging (SWI) in MRI for diagnosing acute stroke.
- To compare Identify any correlations between DWI and SWI findings and the severity or location of acute stroke lesions
- To compare the diagnostic performance of DWI and SWI for acute ischemic stroke detection and assess the correlation between SWI findings and clinical outcomes in stroke patients

METHODOLOGY: A prospective cross-sectional design will be used, Patient of different ages and genders with clinical manifestations of acute stroke, defined as symptoms occurring within 24

hours of onset (e.g., sudden weakness, speech difficulties, visual disturbances, or loss of coordination) referred for MRI examination to Radiology department informed consent on approved format is included in the study. A sample of 87 patients is used for the study.

INCLUSION:

- age limitation 18 TO 95 Years.
- Patients presenting with clinical manifestations of acute stroke, defined as symptoms occurring within 24 hours of onset (e.g., sudden weakness, speech difficulties, visual disturbances, or loss of coordination).

EXCLUSION:

- Contraindications of MRI implants, pacemaker, severe claustrophobic patients.
- Pregnancy, particularly in the first trimester due to potential risks to the fetus.
- Aneurysmal clips.
- Intracellular metallic foreign body.
- Insulin pumps and nerve stimulator.
- RTA.

INSTRUMENT: 3T MRI Siemens Magnetom (Vida) using 16 Chanel head neck coil.

Protocols:

SEQUENCE	SLICE	FOV	THICKNESS	TR (ms)	TE	AVG	PED	POS	SCAN TIME	ACM
AHEAD SCOUT	128	260	1.3-1.5	3.15	1.37	1	A>P R>L	0%	00.14	GRAPPA
T2 TSE TRA	25	220	4-5mm	5000	107	1	R>L	0%	00.40	GRAPPA
T2 TSE FLAIR	25	220	4-5 mm	9000	91	1	R>L	0%	01.50	GRAPPA
DIFFUSION	25	220	4-5 mm	5800	80	1	A>P	0%	2.10	GRAPPA
T2 COR	25	220	4-5 mm	5000	96	1	R>L	0%	00.57	GRAPPA

T2 SAG	25	220	4-5 mm	5600	105	1	A>P	0%	01.04	GRAPPA
T2 SWI TRA	40	220	2.5-3.5	28	20	1	R>L	10%	01.25	GRAPPA
T1 TSE TRA	25	220	4-5	1800	8.40	2	R>L	0%	01.39	GRAPPA

Table-1: Protocols for mri brain stroke protocol

Result: : In this study of 87 patients, MRI Revealed a wide range of brain stroke by DWI & SWI pulse sequence.in the study the most occurred strokes are ischemic stroke(71%) & hemorrhagic stroke(29%).the prevalence rate of acute stroke higher on male then female, male(72%)64 patients & female (28%)23 patients are female. age group mainly (55-65),(65-75),(75-85) age group patients are mostly a high chances of stroke .swi signal are best on hemorrhagic stroke in total sample 25 patients (29%) of hemorrhagic stroke are identified by swi sequence.in our study 43(52.00%)of our cases had lesson LT Side & 24(31.00%) of the patients having stroke lesson on RT side .other sequence T2W,T2W FLAIR Having hyper intensity signal on (100%) of the cases.

GENDER	n=87	In %
MALE	62	72.00%
FEMALE	25	28.00%

Table:1 FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS OF GENDER OF PATIENTS

SWI FINDING	HYPERINTENSE	NO SINNGAL
n=87	63	24

TABLE 2: PATIENTS HAVING SWI FINDING ON THE ACUTE INFRACT PATIENTS

FIGURE 1.1: GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

AGE INTERVAL	n = 87	MALE	FEMALE
18 - 25	7	3	4
25-35	4	3	1
35-45	11	8	3
45-55	13	10	3
55-65	18	16	2
65-75	24	19	5
75-85	16	8	8
85-95	4	3	1

TABLE 3: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS OF PATIENTS

FIGURE 1.2: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTIONS OF AGE OF PATIENTS

FIGURE 1.3: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF SWI FINDING ON HYPERINTENSE OR NO SIGNAL FROM THE ACUTE INFRACT

DWI FINDING	HYPERINTENSE	HYPOINTENSE
N=87	77	10

TABLE 4: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF DWI SIGNAL IN ACUTE STROKE

FIGURE 1.4: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF DWI FINDING ON HYPERINTENSE OR HYPOINTENSE FROM THE ACUTE INFRACT.

SITES	RT SIDE	LT SIDE	B/L
n=87	26	43	14

TABLE 5: FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF SITE OF INFRACT IN BRAIN

Figure 1.5: Frequency Distribution Of Site Of InfRACT In Brain

PATHOLOGIES/ABNORMALITIES	n = 87	In %
Hemorrhagic stroke	25	29.00%
Ischemic stroke	62	71.00%

Table 6: Distributon Of Patients According Type Of InfRACT

Figure1.6: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TYPE OF INFRACT

CONCLUSION: Medical experts mostly employ diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) and conventional MRI for evaluating acute stroke victims. Susceptibility-weighted imaging (SWI), on the other hand, has become a useful adjunct method. Asymmetrically conspicuous hypointense vessels, which might be a sign of underlying problems, can be successfully identified by it. A positive mismatch between DWI and SWI is especially important because it indicates the ischemic penumbra, a region of the brain that is at danger but has not yet suffered irreversible damage, and acts as a marker for infarct growth.

Furthermore, SWI is particularly good in spotting haemorrhages in cases of acute stroke, bringing to light information that conventional MRI sequences might miss. Because of this ability, SWI is a crucial part of the thorough evaluation of stroke patients, improving our knowledge of the illness and perhaps influencing treatment choices. Clinicians can improve patient outcomes by gaining a more detailed understanding of the patient's condition by including SWI into the imaging routine.

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